

Implementation and enablement of FAIR and CARE principled research practice at UniSQ

An implementation project for the Institutional
Underpinnings Program

Project summary report

University of Southern Queensland

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About the Institutional Underpinnings Program

In partnership with 25 Australian universities, we created a jointly-agreed Research Data Management Framework for Institutions for the management, sharing, retention and disposal of research data. Each partner university conducted projects to validate and test an aspect of the framework in their local contexts. This is a report on one of the projects.

More information

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).

View the [Research Data Management Framework for Institutions](#).

Project Summary

The following work was carried out and informed by the [Research Data Management for Institutions Framework](#) (RDM for Institutions Framework) drafting process, working group participation and the RDM draft framework elements:

1. Revision and updating of UniSQ research data management framework (policies, processes, guidelines, and systems).
2. Delivery of information and education sessions and training resources aimed at increasing research staff and students as well as research support staff awareness and understanding of research data management (RDM) principles and practice.
3. Application of FAIR and CARE principles and the learnings from involvement in the development of the RDM for Institutions Framework into identified agricultural and climate research datasets and projects.
4. Documentation and publication of a case study on the experiences of implementing the RDM for Institutions Framework informed RDM at UniSQ.
5. Testing the efficacy and applicability of the RDM for Institutions Framework tools and elements for interoperability with UniSQ's existing and in development systems and program of work.

Resulting Improvements

Resulting improvement at UniSQ as a result of this work includes:

- Provision of clear FAIR and CARE aligned guidelines to research staff and students from the revised procedure and schedules: RD+PM Management Procedure and RDM + Indigenous Data Governance
- Increased awareness at all levels at UniSQ of good research data management practices and knowledge and use of internally and externally available RDM resources.
- Increased engagement and co-working of research support, administration, and central services staff in the coordinated delivery of RDM.
- Improved integration of metadata curation into research project execution, support, and evaluation workflows.
- Increased research data management planning.

Next Steps

The work will continue through:

- Sharing of project outcomes internally and externally to influence good research data management practice.
- Continual application of documented processes to inform the evolution of practices and systems at UniSQ
- Ongoing engagement in and networking with the research data management commons – at State, National and International forums.
- Publication of exemplars to receive feedback and motivate emulation of good practice.

Project Outputs

Reusable outputs produced include:

1. Revised & updated UniSQ [RD+PM Management Procedure](#) and [RDM + Indigenous Data Governance](#) and UniSQ research data management plan and planning process through the Research Information Systems Enhancement project.
2. Revised digital research training course materials and self-help knowledge articles available for research staff and research support staff at UniSQ and more broadly for training shared across data management principles and practice through information and education sessions.
3. FAIR and CARE principles aligned research projects such as: [Northern Australian Climate Program](#) and [Agricultural Research Federation \(AgReFed\) Platform Project](#)
4. Documentation and publication of a case study on the experiences of implementing RDM for Institutions Framework aligned RDM at UniSQ: a. [2021 Collaborative Conference on Computational & Data Intensive Science \(C3DIS\) held online 6 – 8 July](#), b. [2021 Australian Research Management Society Conference held on 3-5 November 2021](#) and c. [Australian Research Data Commons 2022 Data Management Planning – Interest Group Meeting 2 on 19 July 2022](#)
5. Curation of over 40 metadata records in the [UniSQ repository system](#). The metadata records are being further updated for registration with DataCite. Publication of datasets is being progressed.

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).